

EFFECT OF CADMIUM ON LIPID PEROXIDATION AND CATALASE ACTIVITY IN THE TAIL REGION OF EARTHWORM (*APPORCTODEA LONGA*).

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ABSTRACT:

This research studied the biochemical changes measured as the degree of lipid peroxidation and the activity of catalase in the tail region of earthworms (*Apporectodea longa*) maintained in cadmium(Cd) contaminated soils for 7,14 and 21 days. The various concentrations of Cd in the experimentally contaminated sample expressed in mg/kg of soil were 10, 30, 50, 70, 90, 120, 150, 180 and 210 respectively. The effect Cd concentrations on the tail regions of earthworms were measured against control group that was not exposed to Cd. The malondialdehyde (MDA) levels in the control group and the low Cd concentration groups (10-30mg/kg) decreased throughout the study. The mid-level Cd concentration groups (50-120mg/kgCd) had lower MDA levels on day 14 compared to day 7, with observed increase on day 21. The high Cd concentration groups (>120mg/kg) had the lowest MDA concentrations but the highest mortality rates. The catalase activity on day 7 was highest in the concentration 90mgCd/kg soil at 11.77 ± 0.034 nKat/mg protein compared to the corresponding control group (1.77 ± 0.48 nKat/mg protein). The catalase activity on day 14 in the same group was significantly low with a value 0.55 ± 0.04 nKat/mg protein compared to control group. After 21 days, catalase activity was higher in control group compared to other groups exposed to the various concentrations of cadmium. The results indicate that Cd contamination affects biomarkers of oxidative stress in the tail region of earthworms, a reflection of the ecotoxicological effects of Cd to the environment and suggests inhibition of enzyme systems in free radical metabolism.

Keywords: *Cadmium (Cd), Catalase (CAT), Malondialdehyde (MDA), Earthworm*

Introduction:

Heavy metal contamination adversely affects the biotic components of the environment. These adverse effects are products of various metabolic perturbations within the living system (Gupta, 2013; Govind and Madhuri, 2014). Cadmium, a heavy metal is an environmental pollutant released from the mining of metal ores. It is an element obtained for commercial uses principally from cadmium ores called greenockite, commonly found in association with zinc (ATSDR, 1999). It is commonly produced as an inevitable by-product of zinc refining. The most significant uses of cadmium include nickel/cadmium batteries, as anti-corrosives in high stress

environment such as marine and aerospace applications. Other uses include pigment stabilization in polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and as components of alloys. The activities of mining and smelting of ores that contain Cd as an impurity release Cd into the environment contaminating the soil and water bodies (Satarug *et al.*, 2003; Sahmoun, *et al.*, 2005). Over long periods, heavy metals accumulate in the environment with adverse effects on biotic factors (Pal *et al.*, 2006).

Soil organisms provide an accurate reflection of the bioavailability and degree of contamination of heavy metals in their habitat. Observed changes in certain *in vivo* parameters provide early warnings on the nature and effect of the contaminant. Biotests can integrate the harmful and toxic effects of contaminants at the same time within a medium and in combination with chemical analyses, it is possible to generate a natural, reliable and repeatable view of the conditions of the environment (Lukkari, 2004). The limited mobility of earthworms makes them very suitable for monitoring the impact of contaminants (Paoletti, 1999; Diden, 2003). Their non-availability serve as a pointer to soil impairment (Belotti, 1998; Spurgeon and Hopkin, 1996). *A. longa* and other biotic components that inhabit the soil have several functions. They mix and aggregate soil, increase infiltration of the soil encouraging aeration, improve water holding capacity, stimulate microbial activity and provide channels for root growth. These are essential factors that define soil fertility which translates into agricultural yield (Lee, 1985; Edwards and Bohlen, 1996). Several researchers have reported the effects of personal care and pharmaceutical products and other toxic compounds on physical and antioxidant parameters such as earthworm size, structure, reproduction, bioaccumulation and the activity of antioxidant enzymes (Spurgeon and Hopkin, 1996; Wu *et al.*, 2011; Luo *et al.*, 2012). Cd causes oxidative stress in the earthworms that inhabit contaminated areas. Available reports on the oxidative stress parameters in earthworms as biomarkers of metal contamination indicate an overall increase in the entire organism. Since there are indications that enzyme activity is not uniformly distributed along the length of an earthworm (Dallinger, 1993; Morgan and Morgan, 1999), this research evaluated the changes in oxidative stress related biochemical parameters in the tail region. The tail region of the earthworm has been reported to be the region of the earthworm to regenerate the most if amputated (Jamshidi and Pishkahi, 2014). This study was carried out to investigate the effect of metal contamination on the oxidative balance in this region of the earthworm with high capacity to regenerate. The parameters analysed are malondialdehyde (MDA) levels and catalase activity.

Materials and Methods

Collection of experimental animals: The earthworms (*Apporectodea longa*) were collected from a horticultural farm (Santua farms) in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. They were collected by gently digging off the top soil layer and hand picking the earthworms from sub-soil litter. The animals were identified and allowed to acclimatize to laboratory environment for seven days.

Preparation of soil: Soil samples were collected from a pristine site in the University of Benin premises and checked to remove earthworms. From the bulk sample, 1kg soil was weighed and contaminated with various concentrations of Cd chloride (*viz*; 10mg, 30mg, 50mg, 70mg, 90mg,

120mg, 150mg, 180mg and 210mg) mixed thoroughly in a stainless steel bowl with the aid of a spatula and transferred into polythene bags. The bowl was rinsed with 20ml distilled water and poured on the soil sample. Five earthworms with an approximate physical size (length) were kept in each concentration in triplicate and were harvested for analyses on days 7, 14 and 21.

Preparation of earthworms for assay: The tail region (approximately 20th segment from the anterior end) were cut off, weighed and homogenized in normal saline (1:4w/v) using laboratory mortar and pestle on ice cubes. The homogenate was centrifuged at 3500rpm for 5mins. The supernatant was collected with the aid of a micro pipette and refrigerated at 4°C until required for analysis.

Malodialdehyde assay: MDA content was determined using the method described by Buege and Aust (1978). An aliquot of the homogenate supernatant (1.0ml) was mixed with 2ml TCA-TBA-HCl solution. The mixture was heated in a boiling water bath for 15mins. After cooling, the flocculent precipitate was removed by centrifugation at 1000g for 10mins. The absorbance of the sample was determined at 535nm against a blank that contained all the reagents minus the homogenate aliquot supernatant. The MDA concentration was calculated using an extinction coefficient of $1.56 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$.

Calculation:

$$\text{Concentration of MDA in the sample} = \frac{\text{OD/min} \times V \times 1000}{a \times V_s \times l \times W}$$

Where:

OD = absorbance of the test sample at 532nm

V = volume of the reaction mixture

a = Molar extinction coefficient ($1.56 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)

l = length of light path = 1cm

Assay for catalase activity: Catalase activity was measured spectrophotometrically by the method of Cohen et al. (1970). As described by (Obagharhievwo *et al.*, 2012) aliquots of the homogenate supernatant (0.5ml) were added into test tubes in an ice bath while the blank contained 0.5ml distilled water. The reaction was initiated by adding 5ml of cold 30mM H₂O₂ and were mixed thoroughly by inversion. After 3minutes, the reaction was stopped by adding 1ml of 6M H₂SO₄ and mixed quickly by inversion. The test samples and the blank were taken one at a time, 7ml of 0.01M KMnO₄ in 0.05M phosphate buffer pH 7.0 solution was then added and absorbance read at 480 nm within 30-60 sec. The spectrophotometer standard was prepared by adding 7 mL of 0.01M potassium permanganate to a mixture of 5.5 mL of 0.05M phosphate buffer with pH 7.0 and 1 mL of 6M tetraoxosulfate VI acid solution. Activity was expressed as n Kat per mg protein. (1 katal (Kat) = 1mol sec⁻¹)

Calculation:

$$\text{CAT Activity} = \frac{\text{OD/min} * V}{M * V_s * l * y}$$

Where;

OD = absorbance at 480nm

l= light path=1cm

V= total volume of the reaction mixture

V_s= Volume of sample homogenate

M= Molar extinction coefficient of H₂O₂ (40.0M⁻¹cm⁻¹)

y= mg of protein.

Statistical analysis: Values obtained were subjected to Q-test to remove outliers. Only median values within a range were used. The means and standard deviations were calculated using Excel (Microsoft Inc., USA). Two factor ANOVA without replication was used to test for a significance level at p < 0.05 within the various concentrations and the separate days of analyses.

Results

1. MDA Concentration

Table 1: MDA (μmoles/g tissue)

Concentration(mg/kg)	DAY 7 (Mean ± SD) (n)	DAY 14 (Mean ± SD) (n)	DAY 21 (Mean ± SD) (n)
(1) 0	9.61 ± 2.07 (5)	6.41 ± 1.06 (4)	3.87 ± 3.46 (5)
(2) 10	18.66 ± 2.65 (5)	*3.59 (1)	0.47 ± 0.00 (4)
(3) 30	13.09 ± 4.95 (5)	8.76 ± 0.92 (4)	**
(4) 50	14.24 ± 4.96 (5)	20.26 ± 1.82 (4)	28.11 (2)
(5) 70	*34.43 (2)	*9.64 (2)	*9.52 (2)
(6) 90	17.49 ± 1.21 (3)	5.15 (1)	6.22 (1)
(7) 120	13.88 ± 2.18 (5)	5.88 ± 3.06 (3)	45.75 ± 2.33 (4)
(8) 150	14.73 ± 6.01 (2)	*5.5 (1)	*17.9 (1)
(9) 180	7.48 ± 0.52 (2)	5.69 ± 0.16 (5)	*6.63 (1)
(10) 210	5.84 ± 1.03 (5)	*4.63 (1)	2.14 ± 0.11 (3)

n = no of earthworms in each group

* Values resulting from single surviving earthworm

** No surviving earthworm

2. Catalase Activity

Table 2: Catalase activity (n Kat/mg protein)

Concentration (mg/kg)	DAY 7 (n)	DAY 14	DAY 21
0	1.72 ± 0.03 (5)	1.93 ± 0.15 (4)	5.42 ± 0.13 (5)
10	2.71 ± 0.17 (5)	*1.19 (1)	3.01 ± 0.15 (4)
30	2.75 ± 0.06 (5)	1.91 ± 0.04 (4)	**
50	2.79 ± 0.14 (5)	2.46 ± 0.13 (4)	2.84 (1)
70	8.24 ± 0.98 (2)	*1.53 (1)	1.21 ± 0.03 (2)
90	11.77 ± 1.05 (3)	0.55 ± 0.04 (2)	1.69 ± 0.55 (2)
120	2.52 ± 0.10 (5)	1.93 ± 0.10 (3)	2.44 ± 0.15 (4)
150	1.73 ± 0.03 (2)	3.30 ± 0.05 (2)	2.74 ± 0.15 (2)
180	0.76 ± 0.01 (2)	2.40 ± 0.05 (5)	2.03 ± 0.01 (2)
210	0.91 ± 0.03 (5)	*1.10 (1)	0.17 ± 0.01(3)

n = no of earthworms in each group

* Values resulting from the removal of outliers or single surviving earthworm

** No surviving earthworm

Discussion and Conclusion

This research studied the effect of Cd contamination on oxidative stress parameters; MDA and catalase in the tail region of earthworms. Oxidative stress markers are regarded as fast, diagnostic, and prognostic early warning systems to detect the impact of metal contaminants in the environment, which cannot be achieved from mere chemical analysis of environmental samples (Markad *et al.*, 2012).

Earthworms are particularly susceptible to lipid peroxidation due to high content of polyunsaturated fatty acids. Metal contaminants are known to induce lipid peroxidation through the formation of ROS. In this study, the MDA levels were altered after Cd exposure. The responses observed were somewhat variable and without consistent dose–response relationships. This variation may relate to the mechanism of cadmium toxicity to *E. longa* and the MDA levels before the experiment. This is supported by the MDA levels in the control group after 7 days (9.61 ± 2.07 μmoles/g tissue) in the control group. Further analysis for MDA levels in the control group on day 14 and 21 showed a stepwise decrease (6.41 ± 1.06 and 3.87 ± 3.46 μmoles/g tissue respectively) in MDA concentration. This is in tandem with the report by Gao *et al.* (2007). They stated that upon exposure to pollutants, earthworms are able to decrease the toxic effects of chemicals by regulating their internal metabolism. Unlike reports by Wu *et al.* (2011) and Markad *et al.* (2012), peak concentrations of MDA were observed at 10mg/kgCd after 7 days (18.66 ± 2.65 μmoles/g tissue), 50mg/kgCd after 14 days (20.26 ± 1.82 μmoles/g tissue) and 120mg/kgCd (45.75 ± 2.33). Markad *et al.*, 2012 observed an increase in MDA levels in *D. curgensis* after 7 days of fly ash exposure and further increased with an increase in fly ash concentration. Similar observations were reported in *Eisenia fetida* A. and *Polychaeta laenereis* A. exposed to Pb and Cu (Wu *et al.*, 2011). Gao *et al.* (2012) reported that on exposure to

environmental pollutants, earthworms are able to decrease the toxic effects by regulating their internal metabolism. This effect was observed in the low Cd concentration groups (10 and 30 mg/kgCd) in this experiment suggesting that mild concentrations of Cd may be tolerated by *A. longa*. In the middle concentration (50 -120mg/kgCd) groups, earthworms held in 50mg/kgCd and 120mg/kgCd groups had increased levels of MDA concentrations after 21 days whereas a decrease was observed in each of the other concentrations within the range This group had a survival rate lower than the first group suggesting that other factors apart from regulating lipid peroxidation may be involved. These factors were not considered in this experiment. The 120 and 150mg/kg groups had lower levels of MDA on day 14 which were increased beyond the earlier observed concentration (7days) after 21 days. The highest concentrations used for this study had the lowest levels of MDA but had a high mortality rate. This may be due to the inhibition of other biochemical processes.

Catalase is essential to detoxification and plays a key role in cellular antioxidant mechanisms (Wu *et al.*, 2011). In this study, the various concentrations of Cd did not show a significant difference in means in the various groups on all days. However, the results observed were variable compared with dose and duration of exposure suggesting that Cd had altered CAT activity. The control group, lower and the mid- concentration groups showed varying degrees in CAT activity throughout the period of exposure. The 70 and 90mgCd/kg soil group showed an increase in CAT activity after 7days compared to control values. Mortality rate increased from the low Cd concentration to higher Cd concentration groups. The observed low catalase activity in the higher Cd concentration groups is similar to report by Markad *et al.* (2012) and may be attributed to the inhibition of catalase.

In conclusion, Cd affects the oxidative balance in the tail region of *A. longa*. The results obtained are in tandem with previously published literature suggesting the inhibitory effect of Cd in enzyme systems associated with maintenance of oxidative balance. Further research on the mechanisms of the possible inhibitions is suggested.

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